

4.5 “MRV Tools“: A Collection of Practice Abstracts

This subchapter presents three Practice Abstracts focused on Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification (MRV) tools: one explaining the overall methodology for validating GHG assessment tools, and two detailing specific tools tested in Hungary and Denmark.

PRACTICE ABSTRACT #38

SHORT TITLE IN NATIVE LANGUAGE

ESGreen Tool – landbrugets digitale ESG-løsning

SHORT TITLE IN ENGLISH

ESGreenTool – A Digital Sustainability Solution for Danish Agriculture

COUNTRY AND CLIMATIC ZONE

Denmark, north temperate zone

CONTACT

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3 BENEFITS OF THE PRACTICE

1. Calculation of current carbon footprint (CO₂ equivalents) for entire farm, in all production systems
2. Farmers get a prompt overview of measures for reducing C emissions.
3. Calculation of C footprint at product level.

PRODUCTION SYSTEM(S)

Arable crops, beef cattle, dairy cattle, pigs and poultry in organic and conventional.

THEMATIC AREAS

Crops and grassland management, forage production, energy management, herd management, biogas production, rewarding mechanisms, manure storage and spreading.

SUMMARY FOR PRACTICIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN NATIVE LANGUAGE

ESGreen Tool er en digital applikation, der er udviklet i Danmark til at hjælpe landmænd med at beregne og styre deres landbrugs CO₂-fodaftryk. Det blev introduceret i 2022 og er landets første software, der er i stand til at vurdere en gårds udledning af drivhusgasser og udforske potentielle reduktionsstrategier. Beregningsmetoderne bag værktøjet er i overensstemmelse med retningslinjerne fra IPCC 2006 for den nationale opgørelsesrapport på bedriftsniveau og retningslinjerne fra PEF for beregningerne på produktniveau.

Vigtige funktioner:

- **Omfattende emissionsvurdering:** Værktøjet evaluerer udledninger fra forskellige landbrugsaktiviteter, herunder husdyrs fordøjelse, gødningshåndtering, nedbrydning af afgrøderester, energiforbrug og import af ressourcer som foder og dyr.
- **Scenarieanalyse:** Landmænd kan modellere forskellige scenarier for at forstå virkningen af potentielle ændringer i praksis, såsom justeringer i fodersammensætning, gødningsanvendelse eller indførelse af nye teknologier, på deres samlede udledninger.
- **Integration af data:** ESGreen Tool integreres med eksisterende landbrugsdatabaser, hvilket giver mulighed for automatisk dataoverførsel og reducerer manuelt input. Denne integration sikrer, at beregningerne er baseret på nøjagtige og opdaterede oplysninger om gården.
- **Fodaftryk på produktniveau:** I sin avancerede version, ESGreen Tool Climate 2, gør applikationen det muligt for landmænd at beregne klimapåvirkningen pr. produktenhed, f.eks. pr. kg æg, hvilket giver detaljeret indsigt i de udledninger, der er forbundet med specifikke output.

SUMMARY FOR PRACTICIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN ENGLISH

The ESGreen Tool is a digital application developed in Denmark to assist farmers in calculating and managing the carbon footprint of their agricultural operations. Introduced in 2022, it serves as the country's first software capable of assessing a farm's greenhouse gas emissions and exploring potential reduction strategies. The calculation methods behind the tool are aligned with the guidelines of IPCC 2006 as the national inventory report at farm level, and the guidelines of PEF for the calculations at product level.

Key Features:

- **Comprehensive emission assessment:** The tool evaluates emissions from various farm activities, including livestock digestion, manure management, crop residue decomposition, energy consumption, and the import of resources like feed and animals.
- **Scenario analysis:** Farmers can model different scenarios to understand the impact of potential changes in practices, such as adjustments in feed composition, fertilizer application, or the adoption of new technologies, on their overall emissions.
- **Data integration:** ESGreenTool integrates with existing agricultural databases, allowing for automatic data transfer and reducing manual input. This integration ensures that calculations are based on accurate and up-to-date information, specifically concerning the farm.
- **Product-level footprint:** In its advanced version, ESGreenTool Climate 2, the application enables farmers to calculate the climate impact per unit of product, such as per kilogram of eggs, providing detailed insights into the emissions associated with specific outputs.

LONGER DESCRIPTION – IN NATIVE LANGUAGE

ESGreen Tool, der er udviklet af SEGES Innovation og Innovationscenter for økologisk landbrug, er en digital platform til beregning af emissionskilder som en del af ESG-rapporteringen (Environmental, Social and Governance). Værktøjet bruger gården som det system, der vurderes, og det beregner de tre vigtigste drivhusgasser for landbruget: **metan (CH₄)**, **lattergas (N₂O)** og **kuldioxid (CO₂)** i henhold til IPCC's retningslinjer (2006).

Resultaterne er angivet som udledning i **ton CO₂eq pr. år, pr. hektar og pr. kg produkt**. Desuden beregnes en relativ kulstofbalance, som viser, hvor meget kulstof der skønnes at være lagret på gårdens jord. En del af dataene indsamles direkte fra de obligatoriske landbrugsregistreringsdata til den danske regering.

Beregnete emissionskilder:

- Enterisk fermentering/fordøjelse
- Gødning i stald og lager
- Gødning distribueret til markerne
- Omsætning af afgrøderester
- Udvaskning af nitrat
- Energiforbrug og produktion af grøn energi
- Import af ressourcer som foder, halm og dyr
- Balance for kulstofbinding i jorden

ESGreenTool består af to produkter:

- 1. ESGreenTool Climate**, som gør det muligt for landmænd at beregne klimapåvirkningen fra deres landbrugsvirksomhed (Climate 1) og det individuelle produktfodaftrek fra afgrøder og dyr ved hjælp af bedriftsspecifikke data (Climate 2). Det gør det muligt for landmænd at beregne, hvordan potentielle ændringer i f.eks. foder, gødningshåndtering eller ny teknologi vil påvirke gårdens CO₂-fodaftrek eller det specifikke produktfodaftrek for hver produceret enhed. På den måde støtter værktøjet landmanden i at udvikle en konkret plan for at reducere gårdens udledning af drivhusgasser. I øjeblikket er ESGreenTool et afgørende værktøj, da den danske regering har besluttet at reducere udledningen af drivhusgasser fra landbrugssektoren med 55-65 procent inden 2030.
- 2. ESGreenTool-rapporten** giver landmænd mulighed for at dokumentere deres indsats inden for miljø, ledelse og sociale aspekter. Det er en skabelon, der er udviklet til landbruget, med datapunkter, der er relevante for en landbrugsvirksomhed. Det er nemt at vælge og tilpasse 100+ datapunkter baseret på relevante forhold for den enkelte gård (f.eks. udledning af drivhusgasser, arbejdsforhold, biodiversitet, ledelse, dyrevelfærd osv.) Når skabelonen er færdig, kan landmændene nemt dele ESG-data med deres finansielle partnere eller relevante virksomheder i deres værdikæde, og de kan tilpasse den endelige rapport efter deres behov for ESG-data. Outputtet er i pdf-format på gård- og produktniveau.

LONGER DESCRIPTION – IN ENGLISH

The ESGreenTool, developed by SEGES Innovation and Innovation center for organic farming, is a digital platform to calculate emission sources as part of the Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) reporting. The tool uses the farm as the system being assessed and it calculates the three most important greenhouse gases for agriculture: **methane (CH₄)**, **nitrous oxide (N₂O)**, and **carbon dioxide (CO₂)**, according to the IPCC guidelines (2006).

The results are given as emissions in **tons CO₂eq per year, per hectare and per kilogram of product**. In addition, a relative carbon balance is calculated, which shows how much carbon is estimated to be stored on the farms land. Part of the data is collected directly from mandatory farm registration data to the Danish government.

Calculated emission sources:

- Enteric fermentation/digestion

- Manure in barn and stock
- Manure distributed to the fields
- Turnover of crop residues
- Nitrate leaching
- Energy consumption and production of green energy
- Import of resources such as feed, straw, animals
- Carbon sequestration balance in soil

ESGreenTool is made up of two products:

- 1. ESGreenTool Climate**, which allows farmers to calculate the climate impact of their agricultural business (Climate 1) and the individual product footprint of the crops, and animals, using farm specific data (Climate 2). This enables farmers to calculate how potential changes in, for example, feed, fertilizer management, or new technology, will impact the farm's carbon footprint or the specific product footprint for each unit produced. In that way, the tool supports the farmer in developing a concrete plan to reduce the farm's greenhouse gas emissions. Currently, ESGreenTool is a crucial tool, since Danish government has decided to reduce greenhouse gas emissions from agricultural sector by 55-65 percent by 2030.
- 2. ESGreenTool Report** provides a setting for farmers to document their efforts in the areas of environment, governance, and social aspects. It is a template developed for agriculture, with data points relevant to the farming business. It is easy to select and customize 100+ data points based on relevant matters for the individual farm (e.g., greenhouse gas emissions, working conditions, biodiversity, governance, animal welfare etc.). When the template is completed, farmers can easily share ESG data with their financial partners or relevant companies in their value chain, and they can customize the final report according to their demand for ESG data. The output is in pdf format at farm and product level.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

While the ESGreenTool offers valuable insights into sustainability and climate impact on farms, there are some potential downsides:

- 1.** Farmers need to input detailed information about their operations, which can be time-consuming and require a learning curve.
- 2.** The tool integrates with Mark Online, which may limit flexibility for farms that do not already use SEGES systems.

3. The tool has a license fee and depending on the pricing model, smaller farms may find this a limiting factor.
4. If farm data is incomplete or incorrect, the tool's sustainability assessments and CO₂ calculations may not provide a fully accurate picture.
5. As it is developed in Denmark, some of its methodologies or assumptions may not be directly applicable to farms in other countries with different regulations or climatic regions.

PHOTOS

Picture 1: ESGreen Tool calculations - emissions of the three climate gases CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O

Picture 1 shows how ESGreen Tool calculations consider emissions of the three climate gases CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O on a Scope 1 (territorial footprint in relation to the farm emissions e.g., crops, soils, fertilizer usage, number of animals), Scope 2 (energy usage), and Scope 3 (Imports of fertilizer and feed). The application then calculates the climate impact per unit of product in Kg e.g., Kg milk, Kg eggs. (Developed by SEGES Innovation).

ADDITIONAL DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION MATERIAL(S)

Title/Description

ESGreenTool® – the digital solution for environmental, social, and governance (ESG) reporting in agriculture.

URL:

Link [here](#).

Title/Description

Climate footprint at farm level: the importance of imports (Resource in Danish)

URL:

<https://icoel.dk/klima/klimaaftryk-paa-bedriftsniveau-betydningen-af-import/>

PRACTICE ABSTRACT #54**SHORT TITLE IN NATIVE LANGUAGE**

Talajvizsgálat gyorsan és pontosan a termékeny talaj megőrzésének szolgálatában

SHORT TITLE IN ENGLISH

Soil Fertility Management with Innovative Soil Scanner Technology

COUNTRY AND CLIMATIC ZONE

Hungary, continental

CONTACT

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3 BENEFITS OF THE PRACTICE

1. Fast, affordable soil testing with practical results
2. Precision nutrient management via pH, organic matter, texture data
3. Optimized input use for sustainability and lower environmental impact

PRODUCTION SYSTEM

Arable farming, soil fertility management

THEMATIC AREA

Soil Health and Biodiversity, Grassland Management, Crops Management, Water Management, Manure storage and spreading, Energy management

SUMMARY FOR PRACTICIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN NATIVE LANGUAGE

A Talajszkenner egy innovatív eszköz, amely fényvisszaverődés-alapú elemzéssel, „száraz” módszerrel elemzi a talaj kémiai és fizikai jellemzőit. Ez gyorsabb és kényelmesebb alternatívát kínál a hagyományos „nedves” laboratóriumi módszerekhez képest. A szkenner a talaj pH-értékét, szervesanyag-tartalmát (humusz), kötöttségét és fő makroelemek (N, P, K) szintjét méri.

- A talaj pH-ját (H₂O és KCl) a megfelelő kémhatás biztosítására osztályozza, segítve az optimális növénytermesztést.
- Az agyagtartalom %-os megadása alapján a talaj kötöttségére és vízmegtartó képességére vonatkozóan ad információt.
- A szerves C-tartalom mérése révén a humusztartalom pontos becslését teszi lehetővé.

Az eszköz különösen hasznos azoknak a gazdálkodóknak, akik gyorsan szeretnének döntéseket hozni a tápanyag-utánpótlásról és talajmenedzsmentről, minimalizálva a környezetterhelést. A talajszkenner gyakorlati használata több kulcsfontosságú lépést foglal magában. A gazdálkodó vagy a tanácsadó elvégzi a talajmérést, majd a tanácsadó értelmezi az eredményeket, és beépíti azokat a mezőgazdasági döntéshozatalba. A kutatók segíthetnek az adatok elemzésében a finomabb talajgazdálkodási ajánlások érdekében. Az adatok alapján idő- és helyspecifikus tápanyag-gazdálkodási tervet dolgoznak ki, és a gazdálkodó végrehajtja az ajánlott talajkezelési tervet.

A Széchenyi István Egyetemen 2024. november 21-én tartott CODECS éves workshopon 22 résztvevővel a minimális talajművelés, a precíziós gazdálkodás, a talajvizsgálat és az agrárdigitalizáció témakörét járták körül. A digitális talajszkenner legfontosabb előnyei közé tartozik a jobb gazdálkodás, a csökkentett inputköltségek, a jobb pénzügyi kiszámíthatóság, valamint a környezeti előnyök, például az alacsonyabb kibocsátás és a fokozott biológiai sokféleség. A kihívások közé tartoznak a magas beruházási költségek, a korlátozott tanácsadói támogatás, valamint a szakképzés és a fiatalok mezőgazdaságba való bevonásának szükségessége.

SUMMARY FOR PRACTICIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN ENGLISH

The Soil Scanner is an innovative tool that uses light reflection-based analysis to analyze the soil's chemical and physical properties via a "dry"

method. This offers a faster and more convenient alternative to traditional "wet" laboratory techniques. The scanner measures soil pH, organic matter content (humus), soil texture (clay content), and major macronutrients (N, P, K).

- It categorizes soil pH (H₂O and KCl) to ensure optimal conditions for crop production.
- Provides clay content as a percentage, indicating soil texture and water retention capacity.
- Measures organic carbon content, allowing for precise estimation of humus levels.

This tool is especially useful for farmers needing rapid decisions on nutrient management and soil sustainability while reducing environmental impact. The practical use of the Soil Scanner involves several key steps. The farmer or advisor takes the soil measurement, and the advisor then interprets the results and integrates them into farm decision-making. Researchers may assist in data analysis for more refined soil management recommendations. Based on the data, a time- and location-specific nutrient management plan is developed, and the farmer implements the recommended soil treatment plan.

The CODECS annual workshop at Széchenyi István University on November 21, 2024, brought together 22 participants to explore minimum tillage, precision farming, soil testing, and agro-digitalization. Key benefits of digital soil scanners include improved farm management, reduced input costs, better financial predictability, and environmental gains like lower emissions and enhanced biodiversity. Challenges include high investment costs, limited advisor support, and a need for more vocational training and youth involvement in agriculture.

LONGER DESCRIPTION – IN NATIVE LANGUAGE

A Talajszkenner egy olyan eszköz, amely a modern gazdálkodók és agrártanácsadók számára biztosít gyors és pontos talajvizsgáló eredményeket. Fényvisszaverődés-alapú elemzéssel (reflektancia spektroszkópiás elemzés) révén száraz módszerrel vizsgálja a talaj kémiai és fizikai jellemzőit, elkerülve a hagyományos laboratóriumi eljárások idő- és költségigényét.

A Talajszkenner gyakorlati használata több kulcsfontosságú lépésből áll. A gazdálkodó vagy agrártanácsadó elvégzi a talajmintavételt, majd a tanácsadó segít az eredmények értelmezésében és beépítésében a gazdasági döntésekbe. Kutatók is közreműködhetnek az adatelemzésben a

talajgazdálkodás pontosabb ajánlásainak kidolgozásához. Az adatok alapján időzített és helyspecifikus tápanyag-utánpótlási terv készül, amelyet a gazdálkodó végrehajt.

A talajvizsgálatok gyakorisága függ a termesztett növénytől, az évszaktól és a talaj típusától, de az adatalapú gazdálkodás szempontjából a rendszeres ellenőrzés elengedhetetlen. Átlagosan kéthetente a vegetációs időszakban és egyszer szezonon kívül ajánlott a mérések elvégzése.

A CODECS éves workshopját 2024. november 21-én tartották a Széchenyi István Egyetemen, Mosonmagyaróváron, ahol a minimális talajművelés, precíziós gazdálkodás, talajvizsgálat és agrár-digitalizáció témái kerültek fókuszba. Az eseményen 22 résztvevő vett részt, köztük gazdálkodók, tanácsadók és kutatók.

Workshop Eredmények

A résztvevők azonosították a digitális talajszkenner gazdasági, környezeti és gazdálkodási hatásait:

Gazdálkodási Eredmények:

- Hatékonyabb gazdálkodási döntések a pontosabb adatok miatt.
- Nagyobb nyitottság a digitális innovációkra.
- Kevesebb munkavégzés a földeken, mivel csökkenthető a művelési műveletek száma.

Gazdasági Eredmények:

- Csökkentett költségek az optimalizált tápanyag- és növényvédőszer használatával.
- Jobb pénzügyi tervezhetőség a gazdálkodásban.
- Befektetési kihívások, a beruházás megtérülésének bizonytalansága.

Környezeti Eredmények:

- Hatékonyabb inpuhasználat, csökkent műtrágya- és növényvédőszer-felhasználás.
- Biodiverzitás megőrzése precíziós talajgazdálkodással.
- Kevesebb gépi üzemanyag-felhasználás, alacsonyabb karbonlábnyom.

Jóléti Eredmények:

- Kevesebb vegyszerrel való érintkezés a precíziós alkalmazásnak köszönhetően.

- Digitális eszközök segítségével kevesebb stressz és bizonytalanság a gazdálkodásban.

Gazdálkodói Kihívások és Megfontolások

- A digitális technológiák elfogadását nagymértékben befolyásolja a közösségi hatás, a szomszédos gazdák véleménye döntő lehet.
- Szakértői tanácsadás hiányában sok gazdálkodó nem tudja hatékonyan alkalmazni az új technológiákat.
- Hiányzó területek a digitális értékláncban: szakmai képzés és a következő generáció bevonása.

A workshop igazolta, hogy a digitális talajszkenner jelentősen hozzájárul a gazdaságok hatékonyságához, pénzügyi stabilitásához és környezetvédelmi céljaihoz. Míg a gazdasági előnyök azonnal érzékelhetőek, a környezeti hatások hosszabb távon jelentkeznek. Az agrártanácsadók szerepe kulcsfontosságú a gazdálkodók támogatásában az adatvezérelt döntéshozatal és a klímaváltozáshoz való alkalmazkodás terén.

LONGER SUMMARY FOR THE CLIMATE FARM DEMO WEBSITE – IN ENGLISH

The Soil Scanner offers farmers and agricultural advisors a fast and precise method for soil testing, providing key insights into soil health without relying on time-consuming and resource-intensive traditional laboratory techniques. By using reflectance spectroscopy and a dry analysis method, the scanner delivers instant data on soil pH, organic matter content, soil texture (clay content), and major macronutrient levels (N, P, K).

The practical use of the Soil Scanner involves several key steps. The farmer or advisor takes the soil measurement, and the advisor then interprets the results and integrates them into farm decision-making. Researchers may assist in data analysis for more refined soil management recommendations. Based on the data, a time- and location-specific nutrient management plan is developed, and the farmer implements the recommended soil treatment plan.

The frequency of soil scanning depends on the crop type, season, and soil condition, but regular monitoring is essential for data-driven farming. On average, measurements are taken every two weeks during the growing season and once during the off-season.

A CODECS annual workshop was held at Széchenyi István University in Mosonmagyaróvár on November 21, 2024, focusing on minimum tillage,

precision farming practices, soil testing, and agro-digitalization. The event gathered 22 participants, including farmers, advisors, and researchers, with diverse backgrounds and experiences.

Key Outcomes from the Workshop

Participants identified several economic, environmental, and farm management outcomes related to the adoption of digital soil scanners:

Farm Management Outcomes:

- Improved business management due to more measurable farming results.
- Increased readiness to adopt digital innovation.
- Reduced fieldwork time due to fewer cultivation passes.

Economic Outcomes:

- Reduced costs from optimized fertilizer and pesticide use.
- Improved financial predictability for farms.
- Challenges related to investment costs and uncertainty in return on investment.

Environmental Outcomes:

- Optimized farm input efficiency, leading to reduced fertilizer and pesticide use.
- Improved biodiversity due to precise soil nutrient management.
- Lower fuel use and machinery damage, contributing to sustainability goals.

Wellbeing Outcomes:

- Less chemical exposure for farmers due to precision application of inputs.
- Digital tools help in decision-making, reducing stress and uncertainty.

Challenges and Considerations for Farmers

- Adoption of digital tools depends on peer influence, as farmers are more likely to adopt innovations if their neighbors have a positive attitude towards digitalization.
- Farmers without specialist advisors may struggle to integrate new technologies effectively.
- The lack of vocational training and next-generation involvement was identified as a missing area in the value chain.

Conclusion

The workshop confirmed that digital soil scanners contribute significantly to farm efficiency, economic sustainability, and environmental conservation. While economic benefits are immediate (e.g., reduced input costs), environmental improvements occur gradually over time. The role of advisors is critical in guiding farmers towards data-driven decision-making, helping them adapt to climate variability and ensure long-term farm stability.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Facilitating factors for implementation include the scanner's user-friendly interface, mobile connectivity, and compatibility with existing nutrient management systems. However, challenges such as initial investment costs and the need for regular calibration may arise. Future research could focus on expanding the database for local soil types and integrating additional soil health parameters.

Connection with Climate Farm Demo:

- The soil scanner technology empowers **real-time, on-site analysis of soil parameters**, supporting rapid decision-making.
- It enables farmers to **swiftly respond to climate-related soil challenges**, such as nutrient leaching caused by extreme or sudden rainfall.
- By identifying **microelement deficiencies** or imbalances on the spot, farmers can adjust fertilization plans immediately, improving resilience and sustainability.
- The tool contributes to **data-driven, site-specific nutrient management**, a core principle of climate-smart agriculture promoted by the CFD project.
- Its integration into advisory services and demonstration farms **facilitates knowledge transfer**, aligning with CFD's aim to bridge research, innovation, and practice.

PHOTOS

Photo 1: Soil Scanner in Use on Field: An advisor demonstrates the Soil Scanner during a field visit, supporting farmers in data-driven nutrient management.

Photo 2: Efficient Climate Response through Digital Soil Analysis: Real-time interpretation of soil parameters via mobile connectivity empowers on-site decision-making for sustainable farming.

Photo 3: From Soil to Sprout: Understanding your soil's nutrients is the first step to maximizing growth and fertility.

ADDITIONAL DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION MATERIAL(S)

Title/Description

ERASMUS+ WISEFARMER

URL:

<https://food.sze.hu/erasmus-wisefarmer>

Title/Description

SoilCares

URL:

<https://talajszken.com/>

Title/Description

Czernoziom

URL:

<https://www.csernoziom.com/>

Title/Description

CODECS - Innovative Soil Scanner Technology for Sustainable Agriculture

URL:

https://www.horizoncodecs.eu/living_lab/innovative-soil-scanner-technology-for-sustainable-agriculture/

PRACTICE ABSTRACT #57

SHORT TITLE IN ENGLISH

Description of a Methodology for Validating GHG Assessment Tools at Farm Level

COUNTRY AND CLIMATIC ZONE

All countries and all climatic zones concerned

CONTACT

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3 BENEFITS OF THE PRACTICE

1. GHG diagnostic tools identification
2. Carbon tool usability assessment
3. Impact of practices on carbon sensitivity

PRODUCTION SYSTEM

All types of productions

THEMATIC AREA

All

SUMMARY FOR PRACTICIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN NATIVE LANGUAGE

Le projet Climate Farm Demo (CFD) vise à créer un réseau européen d'agriculteurs pilotes. Son objectif global est d'accélérer l'adoption par les agriculteurs de pratiques face au changement climatique. Pour les soutenir

dans cette transition, il leur faut d'abord connaître les émissions de gaz à effet de serre et le stockage de carbone de leur exploitation afin d'élaborer des plans d'action d'atténuation du changement climatique et l'adaptation à ses effets.

De nombreux outils d'évaluation des GES à l'échelle de l'exploitation existent pour les différents systèmes agricoles. Les outils sélectionnés doivent être d'une qualité suffisante et répondre à certaines normes scientifiques. Pour évaluer les outils, nous avons utilisé une approche par étapes : 1) définition des critères d'évaluation, 2) collecte d'informations sur les outils, 3) réalisation de l'évaluation et 4) fourniture de fiches d'information sur les outils sélectionnés. Les informations suivantes ont été collectées pour évaluer les outils :

- Informations générales
 - Systèmes de production couverts
 - Langues disponibles
 - Périmètre de l'évaluation de l'outil
 - Coût d'utilisation
- Caractéristiques pour l'élaboration d'un plan d'action
 - Description de l'exploitation
 - Unités fonctionnelles émissions de GES et stockage
 - Comparaison des résultats des références
 - Autres impacts environnementaux
 - Liste de leviers d'atténuation
 - Lien avec les résultats économique
 - Possibilité de simuler les plans d'action
- Support aux conseillers
 - Modalités de formation
 - Documentation
 - Export / Import de données
- Sensibilité aux pratiques
 - Fermentation entérique
 - Gestion des effluents
 - Gestion de l'azote sur les surfaces
 - Consommation d'énergie
 - Facteurs d'émissions des engrais
 - Facteurs d'émissions des aliments
 - Stockage de carbone

Sur la base de cette évaluation, le projet a sélectionné 18 outils qui peuvent être utilisés par les agriculteurs et les conseillers dans le cadre du projet Climate Farm Demo, et qui couvrent les principaux systèmes de production

agricole. Ces outils sont compilés sur le site du projet : <https://climatefarmdemo.eu/cfd/en/#/resources>

SUMMARY FOR PRACTITIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN ENGLISH

The Climate Farm Demo project aims to create a unique pan-European network of Pilot Demo Farmers. Its overall objective is to accelerate the adoption of Climate Smart Farming practices and solutions by farmers. To support farmers in this transition, they first need insight into current GHG emissions and carbon removals on their farms to create action plans for climate change mitigation and adaptation.

Over the last decade, a range of farm-level GHG assessment tools have been developed for different farming systems. The main objective of these tools is to help farmers and advisors determine their baseline GHG emissions and assist in developing action plans. The selected tools should be of sufficient quality and comply with a certain scientific standard.

To evaluate the tools, we used a stepwise approach: 1) define evaluation criteria, 2) collect tool information, 3) perform assessment, and 4) provide information sheets on the selected tools.

The following information was collected to evaluate the tools:

General information

- Covered production systems
- Available languages
- Scope of the tool
- Cost of the tool

Features for development of an action plan

- Description of farms
- Type of GHG emissions and carbon storage included
- Benchmark possibility
- Other environmental impacts
- List of mitigation options
- Economic impact results
- Action plan simulation possibility

Support for advisors

- Training possibilities (cost, format, support)
- Documentation (user guide, methodology)
- Data handling

Sensitivity to mitigation practices

- Enteric fermentation
- Manure management
- Nitrogen management in the field
- Energy consumption
- Fertilizer emission factors (related to production emissions)
- Feed emission factors
- Carbon storage

Based on the assessment, the project selected 18 tools that can be used by farmers and advisors in the project, which cover the major agricultural production systems. These tools are compiled on the project website: <https://climatefarmdemo.eu/cfd/en/#/resources>.

LONGER DESCRIPTION – IN NATIVE LANGUAGE

Le projet Climate Farm Demo vise à créer un réseau européen d'agriculteurs pilotes. Son objectif est d'accélérer l'adoption par les agriculteurs de pratiques face au changement climatique en vue d'adapter les systèmes de production et de parvenir à un secteur agricole neutre en carbone d'ici à 2050. Pour soutenir les agriculteurs dans cette transition, il leur faut d'abord connaître les émissions de GES et le stockage de carbone de leurs exploitations afin de créer des plans d'action pour l'atténuation du changement climatique et l'adaptation à celui-ci.

Au cours de la dernière décennie, différents d'outils d'évaluation des GES à l'échelle de l'exploitation ont été mis au point pour différents systèmes agricoles. La plupart ont été développés pour calculer l'empreinte carbone des produits agricole. D'autres outils ont été développés au niveau de l'exploitation pour fournir des informations sur les flux d'éléments nutritifs et les émissions au sein du système.

L'objectif principal de l'utilisation de ces outils est d'aider les agriculteurs et les conseillers à déterminer leurs émissions de GES de référence et de contribuer à l'élaboration des plans d'action. La comparaison des performances des exploitations agricoles en matière d'émissions de gaz à effet de serre entre les pays n'est pas l'objectif du projet. Par conséquent, le projet a décidé de ne pas utiliser un seul outil pour toutes les exploitations, mais de permettre aux agriculteurs et aux conseillers de travailler avec les outils qu'ils utilisent déjà dans leur pays. Toutefois, les outils sélectionnés doivent être d'une qualité suffisante et répondre à certaines normes scientifiques. Voici les étapes suivies et les critères observés pour valider les outils.

Première sélection :

Seuls les outils répondant aux critères suivants peuvent être pris en compte pour la suite de l'évaluation :

1. Outil qui évalue les émissions de GES couvrant les scopes 1, 2 et 3 d'une exploitation agricole.
2. Outil dont le développement est suffisamment avancé pour pouvoir être utilisés directement par les agriculteurs/conseillers dans le cadre de l'élaboration des plans d'action.
3. Outil qui dispose d'une documentation suffisante pour réaliser l'évaluation (description de la méthodologie).

Voici ensuite les informations importantes à observer pour évaluer les outils. Informations sur les caractéristiques pertinentes pour l'élaboration d'un plan d'action pour les exploitations agricoles. Un aspect important est de savoir dans quelle mesure les outils sont sensibles à certaines pratiques d'atténuation, étant donné que les pratiques qui seront mises en œuvre dans ces exploitations devraient idéalement être reflétées dans l'évaluation suivante des GES.

Vous trouverez ci-dessous la liste complète des sujets à prendre en considération :

- Informations générales
 - Systèmes de production couverts
 - Langues disponibles
 - Périmètre de l'évaluation de l'outil
 - Coût d'utilisation
- Caractéristiques pour l'élaboration d'un plan d'action
 - Description de l'exploitation
 - Unités fonctionnelles émissions de GES et stockage
 - Comparaison des résultats des références
 - Autres impacts environnementaux
 - Liste de leviers d'atténuation
 - Lien avec les résultats économique
 - Possibilité de simuler les plans d'action
- Support aux conseillers
 - Modalités de formation (coût, format, support après formation)
 - Documentation (guide utilisateur, méthodologie)
 - Export / Import de données
- Sensibilité aux pratiques
 - Fermentation entérique
 - Gestion des effluents
 - Gestion de l'azote sur les surfaces

- Consommation d'énergie
- Facteurs d'émissions des engrais
- Facteurs d'émissions des aliments
- Stockage de carbone

Sur la base de cette évaluation, le projet a sélectionné 18 outils qui peuvent être utilisés par les agriculteurs et les conseillers dans le cadre du projet Climate Farm Demo, et qui couvrent les principaux systèmes de production agricole. Voici la liste des outils sélectionnés : Agnav, Agrecalc, Agrösfar, Biocode, Bovid CO2, CAP'2ER, Carbon F&L, Convis, Cool Farm Tool, DECiDE, ES Green Tool, Farm Carbon Calculator, Geep, GES&VIT, Klimrek, KLIR, Kringloopwijzer (ANCA), TEKla.

LONGER DESCRIPTION – IN ENGLISH

The Climate Farm Demo (CFD) project aims to create a unique pan-European network of Pilot Demo Farmers covering 27 countries and all pedo-climatic areas. Its overall objective is to accelerate the adoption of Climate Smart Farming practices and solutions by farmers with a view to adapting agricultural production systems to climate change and to achieving a carbon neutral agricultural sector by 2050. To support farmers in this transition they first need insight in the current GHG emissions and carbon removals on their farms in order to create action plans for climate change mitigation and adaptation.

Over the last decade a range of farm level GHG assessment tools have been developed for different farming systems. Most tools were developed to calculate the carbon footprint of crops or livestock products, which is increasingly being demanded by the food industry. Other tools were developed as farm level tools to provide insights in nutrient flows and emissions on the farm. Some tools are more appropriate as monitoring tools, whereas others have possibilities to also perform simulations with alternative management, which can be used for creating action plans.

Also, geographically there is a large variation, where countries in Western Europe have multiple tools available, while in Central-eastern European countries often no tools are yet developed.

The main objective for the use of these tools is to help farmers and advisors to determine their baseline GHG emissions and to assist in the development of the action plans. A comparison of the GHG performance of farms among countries is not the focus of the project. Therefore, the project decided not to use only a single tool for all farms but instead allow farmers and advisors to work with the tools they already might use in their country. However, the

selected tools should be of sufficient quality and comply with to a certain scientific standard. Here are the steps followed, and the criteria observed to validate the tools.

First screening:

Only tools meeting the following criteria can be considered for further evaluation:

1. Tool that assesses a farm's GHG emissions covering scopes 1, 2 and 3
2. Sufficiently advanced in their development so that the tool can be used directly by farmers/advisors for the development of the action plans and
3. Sufficient documentation material should be available to perform the evaluation.

Next, here is the important information to observe to evaluate the tools: Information on features that are relevant for the development of an action plan for the farms. An important aspect is to what extent the tools are sensitive to certain mitigation practices, as the practices that will be implemented on those farms should ideally be reflected in the following GHG assessment. Below the full list of topics to be considered:

- General information
 - Covered production systems
 - Available languages
 - Scope of the tool
 - Cost of the tool
- Features for development of an action plan
 - Description of farm
 - Type of GHG emissions and carbon storage included
 - Benchmark possibility
 - Other environmental impacts
 - List of mitigation options
 - Economic impact results
 - Action plan simulation possibility
- Support for advisors
 - Training possibilities (cost, format, support)
 - Documentation (user guide, methodology documentation)
 - Data handling
- Sensitivity to mitigation practices
 - Enteric fermentation
 - Manure management

- Nitrogen management in the field
- Energy consumption
- Fertilizer emission factors (related to production emission)
- Feed emission factors
- Carbon storage

Based on the assessment, the project selected 18 tools that can be used by farmers and advisors in the Climate Farm Demo project, which cover the major agricultural production systems. Here is the list of selected tools: Agnav, Agrecalc, Agrösfar, Biocode, Bovid CO2, CAP'2ER, Carbon F&L, Convis, Cool Farm Tool, DECiDE, ES Green Tool, Farm Carbon Calculator, Geep, GES&VIT, Klimrek, KLIR, Kringloopwijzer (ANCA), TEKla.

PHOTOS

Figure 1: GHG Assessment and number of tools